

CHAPTER 2

Methodology and Study Design - An introduction to Density Functional Theory

"ab-initio" literally means "from the beginning". In material science, the term ab-initio is used for the vast theoretical concepts and computational methods that are used to explore the electronic structure or nuclear dynamics of solids based on principles of quantum mechanics [36]. Empirical results or extrapolated/interpolated information of adjustable variables are not considered in an *ab initio* scheme [37]. Material modeling based on ab-initio methods has grown enormously in the last few decades, which is made possible by new simulation techniques and an immense increase in computational power. The modelling has significantly been augmented with advancement of quantum mechanical Schrodinger wave approach followed by seminal work by Dirac, Fermi, Hartree, Fock, Hohenberg, Kohn, Sham, and others for implementing the quantum mechanics principles to crystalline materials. Prior to that, force field schemes were usually employed in which forces that govern the interatomic interactions are parameterized to reproduce a series of empirical data such as bulk modulus, equilibrium geometries, or vibrational frequencies. However, the approach has reached a high level of complexity and are often employed for a certain class of materials in which good parameters are already known from closely related systems. Nonavailability of such parameters or in cases where system depicts unusual behavior then ab-initio computations are typically required. The benefit of the first principle approaches (ab-initio) is that they can be performed without experimental information. In 1964-1965, Hohenberg, Kohn, and Sham established the density functional theory (DFT) and turned it into a realistic tool for exploring material properties [38,39]. Later on, DFT became the workshop for material modeling and simulations. The DFT approach

includes everything needed to model the physical properties of any material from unit cell structure, utilizing computer. In this work, stability, electronic-magnetic, transport, and other properties of some double perovskites have been investigated via ab-initio calculations. As a result, this chapter is about discussing and understanding the underlying quantum mechanical concepts of DFT. Because the topic is so vast, only the main concepts and relevant equations are introduced, complete derivation of the DFT techniques is omitted.

2.1 Schrodinger Wave equation

Quantum mechanicals is based on the concept of wave function. Wave function gives access to all information of the system, if the wave function is known everything about the system can be determined. So, a general approach to every problem is to determine exactly or by approximate means wave function from the Schrodinger Wave equation (SWE). It is a partial differential equation given by [40]

$$\hat{H}\psi(r, R) = E\psi(r, R) \quad (2.1)$$

$\psi(r, R)$ represent the total wave function, it is the function of electronic and nuclear spatial coordinates. \hat{H} symbolizes Hamiltonian operator, for a many-body system is given by;

$$\hat{H} = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2M_N} \sum_I \nabla_{R_I}^2 - \frac{\hbar^2}{2m_e} \sum_i \nabla_{r_i}^2 + \frac{e^2}{2} \sum'_{i,j} \frac{1}{|r_i - r_j|} + \frac{e^2}{2} \sum'_{I,J} \frac{Z_I Z_J}{|R_I - R_J|} - \frac{e^2}{2} \sum_{I,i} \frac{Z_I}{|R_I - r_i|} \quad (2.2)$$

here, m_e , r_i , and e are used to represent mass, position coordinates, and charge of electron respectively. Similarly, M_N , R_I , and Z represent the corresponding parameters for nucleus. Primes over summation are used to rule out equality of subscripts. In short notation equation 2.2 can be written as;

$$\hat{H} = T_N(R_I) + T_e(r_i) + V_{ee}(r_i, r_j) + V_{eN}(r_i, R_I) + V_{NN}(R_I, R_J) \quad (2.3)$$

$T_N(R_I)$ and $T_e(r_i)$ symbolizes the total kinetic energy of nuclei and electrons, respectively. Correspondingly, $V_{ee}(r_i, r_j)$, $V_{eN}(r_i, R_I)$ and $V_{NN}(R_I, R_J)$ represent potential energy due to electron-electron, electron-nuclei, and nuclei-nuclei interaction. The Schrodinger approach to problem can be systematically represented in sequence as:

Specify the problem, i.e., define $V(r, R)$, substitute it in SWE and determine wavefunction. Finally, compute the expectation values to acquire observables. Unfortunately, the SWE can only be solved exactly for a single electron system- Hydrogenic atoms. Even when switching from hydrogen to helium, no analytical solutions for SWE are known, forcing the use of approximation approaches to tackle the problem.

Further, the interactions of charged particles produce quantum correlations. As a result, the movement of a single electron is associated with the movement of all other electrons in the system. Thus, analytical solutions are unpractical or even impossible to obtain. The exchange-correlation coupling further doesn't allow decoupling the problem to single-electron problems. Also, interactions are so strong that they cannot be handled as a perturbation. Several approximations have been made to simplify the many body problem. The efforts made in formulating the approximations to solve the problem are undoubtedly worthwhile because knowledge of electron structure allows one to study physical aspects such as equilibrium structure, magnetic, transport and mechanical behavior, and so on.

2.2 Born-Oppenheimer, Adiabatic and Classical Approximation

The mass of the nucleus is several tens of thousand times the mass of electron (M_N is roughly 30,000 times greater than m_e in O_8^{16}), as a result, the nucleus moves significantly slower than electrons. The electron-wave function instantly adjusts to a relative position of the vibrating ions: the electrons move rapidly without changing their stationary state - adiabatic motion. Ions, on the other hand, follow their dynamics, the moving electron's charge merely forms a uniformly smeared/diffused background for nuclei. As a result, electrons and ions might be considered independent subsystems. Born-Oppenheimer [41,42] therefore, decoupled the nuclei and electron motion substituted total wave function as a product of nuclear wavefunction $\psi_N(R)$ which is only a function of nuclear coordinates and electronic wavefunction $\psi_e(r)$ whi-

ch is only a function of electronic coordinates periodic field.

$$\psi(r, R) = \psi_N(R)\psi_e(r) \quad (2.4)$$

Due to large nuclear mass, nuclear wave packets are localized, thus nuclei can be treated as classical particles following Newtonian type equation of motion - Classical approximation. The error in the approximation is proportional to the anharmonicity of the vibrations and the spatial extent of the nuclear wave packet. Nuclear vibrations are minimal at low temperatures because nuclei vibrate solely about their equilibrium position. Therefore, nuclei can be treated to be frozen at equilibrium positions, electrons are therefore the only players in the game of many-body problem. As a result, nuclei's kinetic energy diminishes, while the nuclei-nuclei potential merely turns out to be a constant. Thus, after applying Born-Oppenheimer approximation, all that is required is the search for an electronic wave function based on electron coordinates. However, electron-nuclear interactions are still there, these can be regarded as a 'external Potential $V(r)$ ', experienced by an electron cloud in a periodic field.

$$\{T_e(r_i) + V_{ee}(r_i, r_j) + V_{eN}(r_i, R_I)\}\psi_e(r) = E_e\psi_e(r) \quad (2.5)$$

In the electronic structure problem, R_I only appears as a parameter. The first-order correction to the approximation owing to electron-nuclear coupling is of order of $[m_e/M_N]^{1/4}$. Even though the Born-Oppenheimer approximation simplifies SWE, however, many body systems can't be still easily solved with the approach. Because still, N-electron body system requires $3N$ coordinates (keeping spin coordinates aside).

2.3 From Many-Particle Hamiltonian to Self-Consistent Field Approach

The interacting potential make the problem complicated, in order to avoid the interacting picture, Hartree [43,44] came up with the idea that electron in a system move in the 'averaged effective potential V_{eff} '. As a result, the interacting many-electron system is reduced to a non-interacting single electron problem. V_{eff} is self-consistently determined by all other electrons present in the system. The independent electron model enables to write the many-electron wave function as a simple product of a one-electron wave function, $\varphi_i^H(r_i)$, called Hartree product. periodic field.

$$\psi_e(r) = \psi_e(r_1, r_2, r_3 \dots r_N) = \varphi_1^H(r_1)\varphi_2^H(r_2)\varphi_3^H(r_3) \dots \varphi_N^H(r_N) \quad (2.6)$$

Individual electron wave functions are anticipated to be normalized but not necessarily orthogonal; the product ensures that the total electron wave function is also normalized. As a result, the energy's expected value would be

$$\langle E \rangle = \langle \psi_e(r_1, r_2, r_3 \dots r_N) | \hat{H} | \psi_e(r_1, r_2, r_3 \dots r_N) \rangle \quad (2.7)$$

To construct the ground state wave function Hartree used the variation principle - It states that if a system is characterized by an unknown parameter, the value of the parameter that best defines the system is the one that corresponds to the lowest energy. So, the energy from equation 2.7 must be larger than or equal to the ground-state energy; however, the equality condition is only satisfied when the

approximate wavefunction is the exact wave function. This procedure from equation 2.7 leads to a set of Hartree equations

$$\left[-\frac{\hbar}{2m_e} \nabla^2 + V_{eff} \right] \varphi_i^H(r_i) = \varepsilon_i \varphi_i^H(r_i) \quad (2.8)$$

$$\text{where, } V_{eff} = V_{ext}(r_i) + V_{ee}(r_i, r_j) = V_{ext}(r_i) + e^2 \int \frac{\sum_{i,j} |\varphi_j^H(r_j)|^2}{|r_i - r_j|} dr_j \quad (2.9)$$

The electron-electron interaction energy can be further simplified by expressing in terms of electron density - Hartree energy (V_H)

$$\langle V_{ee} \rangle = V_H = e^2 \iint \frac{\sum_{i,j} n(r_i)n(r_j)}{|r_i - r_j|} dr_i dr_j \quad (2.10)$$

This is nothing new just electron-electron Coulomb repulsion in terms of electron charge density, $n(r_i) = |\varphi_i^H|^2 \cdot V_{eff}$ and $\varphi(r_i)$'s are interrelated, to compute one, the other must be known. Indeed, self-consistent field (SCF) method can be implemented to simplify Hartree equations. Therefore, a trial wave function is assumed to compute V_{eff} and then recalculate the eigenstates, repeatedly. This approach yields a set of eigenstates that are consistent with the potential. However, Hartree treated electrons as distinguishable particles, moreover, exchange and correlation interaction are missing. To introduce the indistinguishable fermionic character of electrons in Hartree theory, Fock used the antisymmetric wavefunction (Slater determinant) instead of simple product one electron wave function as a trial wave function [107,108]

$$\psi_e(r_1, r_2, r_3 \dots r_N) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N!}} \begin{vmatrix} \varphi_1^{HF}(r_1) & \dots & \varphi_1^{HF}(r_N) \\ \dots & \dots & \dots \\ \varphi_N^{HF}(r_1) & \dots & \varphi_N^{HF}(r_N) \end{vmatrix} \quad (2.11)$$

Variational calculation of the expectation value of energy as in equation 3.7 putting with equation 2.11 leads to set of Hartree-Fock (HF) equations

$$\left[-\frac{\hbar}{2m_e} \nabla_{r_i}^2 + V_{ext}(r_i) + \int \frac{\sum_{i,j} |\varphi_i^{HF}(r_j)|^2}{|r_i - r_j|} dr_j \right] \varphi_i^{HF}(r_i) - \sum_{j \neq i} \left[e^2 \int \frac{\varphi_j^{HF*}(r_j) \varphi_i^{HF}(r_i)}{|r_i - r_j|} dr_j \right] \varphi_j^{HF}(r_j) = \varepsilon_i \varphi_i^{HF}(r_i) \quad (2.12)$$

HF equations look similar to Hartree equations, the extra term (3rd term on left side) in the equation 2.12 in comparison to the Hartree equation is the exchange interaction. It is different from direct interactions which are also present in the Hartree approximation. The exchange integrals introduce additional coupling terms which arise from every pair of parallel electrons. Although HF completely ignores the electronic correlations, still, it explains chemical bonding in solids and has remained the choice of chemists to study the electronic structure. However, computational demands increase exponentially with the number of electrons. Still N-single electron system requires 3N spatial coordinates, therefore is not appropriate for a system with a large number of interacting particles.

2.4 Density Functional Theory - From Wave Functions to Electron Density

Solving the SWE for $\psi_e(r_i)$ seems a daunting task even for the smallest system. Up to now, the $\psi_e(r)$ is described as a basic variable, however, $\psi_e(r)$ of a system can't be directly probed. The physically significant parameter is the probability, $|\psi_e(r)|^2$. The probability amplitude of finding an electron at position r is equivalent to electron charge density, $n(r)$. For a many body system with N-electrons the electron charge density is given by

$$n(r) = N \int \psi_e^*(r, r_2, r_3 \dots r_N) \psi_e(r, r_2, r_3 \dots r_N) dr_2 \dots dr_N \quad (2.13)$$

It is a non-negative variable, vanishes at infinity, and integrates into the total number of electrons. Unlike wavefunction, the electron density can be measured experimentally. Moreover, $n(r)$ is a function of just three spatial variables, unlike $\psi_e(r)$ which is a function of 3N variables. Can $n(r)$ replace wavefunction as a

basic variable for computation purpose? Of course, Yes! In the meantime, analogous to Hartree's theory, Thomas and Fermi proposed electronic density could be used as the fundamental variable to explore the electronic structure of the solids - Thomas Fermi model . However, the model doesn't prove worthwhile because of crude assumptions particularly for kinetic energy and ignorance of exchange and correlation effects. However, the essence of the model is to circumvent the wave function approach, concentrating on density as a basic variable. It became the starting point for the development of DFT which nowadays is widely used to conduct electronic structure calculations in condensed matter physics. At the heart of DFT are the Hohenberg-Kohn (HK) theorems [47,48].

2.5 Hohenberg-Kohn Theorems

First Theorem: The external potential $V_{\text{ext}}(r)$ of any system is univocally described by charge density $n(r)$, with an additive constant, i.e., $V_{\text{ext}}(r)$ and $n(r)$ has one-to-one correspondence [48]. This implies two different potentials will never correspond to the same density, so, $n(r)$ determines $V_{\text{ext}}(r)$. $V_{\text{ext}}(r)$ itself fixes \hat{H} which in turn fixes $\psi_e(r)$. This means the wave function is a functional (function of function) of density, $\psi[n(r)]$. If the wavefunction can be determined from density and vice-versa, then both functions are equivalent and contain the same information. Consequently, all other ground state parameters are functionals of density. Thereby the DFT approach to any problem can be systematically represented in sequence as ;i.e., knowledge of $n(r)$ implies knowledge of the potential and wave function, and hence of all other observables. This theorem thereby endorses charge density as a key parameter sufficient to obtain all properties of interest. But, how can we be sure that a certain density is the density that we are looking for? This ambiguity was cleared via the second theorem.

Second Theorem:

There exists a universal function of density $F[n(r)]$ independent of external potential such that for some given $V_{\text{ext}}(r)$ the energy functional can be defined as ;

$$E[n] = \int V_{\text{ext}}(r)n(r)dr + F[n(r)] \quad (2.14)$$

The first term is non-universal as it depends on external potential but once the system is specified, i.e. when $V_{\text{ext}}(r)$ is fixed, the functional is known explicitly. The universal function $F[n(r)] = \langle \psi_e | T + V_{ee} | \psi_e \rangle$ has a similar form for every electronic structure problem. In search for true ground state density, Hohenberg and Kohn implemented the variational principle in the state-of-art formulism, the density that minimizes the total energy given in equation 2.14 represents the true ground state density.

2.6 Kohn-Sham Equation

Despite the fact that Hohenberg-Kohn described total energy in terms of the universal functional $F[n(r)]$, however, the exact form of $F[n(r)]$ was unknown. Kohn and Sham (KS) [49-50] employed assumptions similar to Hartree's and proposed a systematic approach for the hitherto unknown $F[n(r)]$. KS mapped many-body problem with interaction potentials onto an independent single-body problem without interaction potentials. Consider a hypothetical system made up of non-interacting electrons experiencing mean potential V_s . Because the system has no interactions, the exact wave function for such a system is a Slater determinant. The kinetic energy (KE) of such a system would thus be;

$$T_s = -\frac{1}{2m_e} \sum_i \langle \varphi_i^{ks} | \nabla^2 | \varphi_i^{ks} \rangle \quad (2.15)$$

For this system, the expected value of V_s would be classical Hartree potential energy. Even if the fictional and real systems have the same density, the fictitious system's KE will never match the true KE of the real system. The residual component of kinetic energy and potential that the fictional system does not cover

is simply added to the non-classical exchange-correlation (E_{xc}) part. This is done by splitting universal functional as; $F[n(r)] = T_S + V_H + E_{xc}$. The connection between this fictitious system and the real system is framed by setting V_{ks} such that both systems share the same ground-state density i.e.,

$$n_s(r) = \sum_i |\varphi_i^{ks}(r_i)|^2 = n_{\text{real}}(r) \quad (2.16)$$

But how can the potential V_S be specified such that both systems (fictitious and real) share the same density? The most efficient way is to utilize the variational principle and minimise the energy functional $E[n] = \int V_{\text{ext}}(r)n(r)dr + T_S + V_H + E_{xc}$, by introducing orbitals constrained by orthonormal condition and then constructing the densities as a sum over occupied orbitals. This technique yields a set of single-particle Schrödinger like equations known as Kohn-Sham equations

$$\left[-\frac{\hbar}{2m_e} \nabla^2 + V_{ks} \right] \varphi_i^{KS}(r_i) = \varepsilon_i \varphi_i^{KS}(r_i) \quad (2.17)$$

where $V_{ks} = V_{\text{ext}} + V_H + V_{xc}$. In the formulism, V_{xc} is only unknown can be written as;

$$V_{xc} = \frac{\delta E_{xc}[n(r)]}{\delta n(r)} \quad (2.18)$$

To solve the KS equations, we must first establish the Hartree potential, which requires knowledge of $n(r)$. However, in order to get the electron density, we must first determine the single-electron KS orbitals, φ_i^{KS} , which requires solving the KS equations. The problem is commonly approached iteratively, as outlined below [51]:

Step 1: Define trial $n(r)$ by using electron orbitals modelled through basis set.

Step 2: Solve KS equations for φ_i^{KS} using trial $n(r)$.

Step 3: Compute $n(r)$ with the help of φ_i^{KS} from Step 2.

Compare trial $n(r)$ and computed $n(r)$; if the two densities are same, then it represents the ground state electron density. However, if the densities are dissimilar, then the trial electron density had to be revised. This is often accomplished by feeding the output of Step 3 into Step 2 and repeating the procedure until the charge density in subsequent cycles converges. This iterative mechanism can lead to a solution of the KS equations that are self-consistent.

2.7 Exchange-Correlation Functional - Making DFT a Practical Tool

Although Hartree potential can be estimated from the trial density, the state-of-the-art formulism still has one unknown parameter that must be approximated. For computing purposes, DFT would have been an exact theoretical approach, if exchange-correlations (quantum mechanical interactions) were certainly known. All the unknown parameters of the total energy are collectively clubbed into single exchange-correlation functional $\epsilon_{xc}[n(r)]$. It includes a non-classical component of the electron-electron interaction as well as lacking part of kinetic energy that is not covered by the fictitious reference system

$$\epsilon_{xc}[n(r)] = T(n) - T_S(n) + V_{ee} - V_H \quad (2.19)$$

For a weakly correlated system this energy is often substantially smaller compared to the single particle energies. However, for systems mainly composed of d/f elements this energy is of the order of single-particle energies - strongly correlated. Correlation is a quantum mechanical effect of how the movement of electron is influenced by the presence of all other electrons. Correlation energy can also be thought of as an energy decrease in a real system caused by the mutual avoidance of interacting electrons to be at some position. Since the Hartree-Fock scheme only involves exchange and not correlation effects, thereby correlation

energy can be defined as energy difference between real and Hartree Fock systems, $E - E_H$. Whilst exchange energy refers to the energy reduction in an actual system as a result of Pauli's principle, which prevents two identical spin electrons from occupying the same orbital and so to reduces Pauli repulsion. As the Hartree approach excludes both exchange and correlation, the energy difference $E_{HF} - E_H$ is therefore equivalent to exchange energy. Up to here, no approximation was used in the DFT; nevertheless, the uncertain nature of $\epsilon_{xc}[n(r)]$ forces approximations to be implemented. Thus, an assumption is looked-for to turn DFT into a practical tool for ab-initio calculations of electronic structure. The accuracy of DFT approach hinges exclusively on how accurately $\epsilon_{xc}[n(r)]$ can be approximated. As a result, the quest of ever-better functionals remains at the center of DFT ab-initio computation .

2.8 Local Density Approximations (LDA)

Almost all the approximations used today to estimate $\epsilon_{xc}[n(r)]$ are extensions of the LDA model. LDA is centred around a hypothetical homogenous electron gas - a key element of DFT since it is the only system for which $\epsilon_{xc}[n(r)]$ can be measured exactly or with high accuracy. The estimated value of $\epsilon_{xc}[n(r)]$ by LDA method is given by;

$$\epsilon_{xc}^{LDA} = \int n(r)\epsilon_{xc}[n(r)]dr \quad (2.20)$$

where, $\epsilon_{xc}[n(r)]$ represents the exchange-correlation energy per particle at point r . This energy per particle is weighted with the probability $n(r)$ that there is in fact an electron at r . LDA is practically exact for uniform electron gas or for systems with slow varying densities with respect to coordinates. However, even in solid with complex structures, the LDA has proven to be quite effective as it is fast and produces acceptable results. This can be partly ascribed to the fact that LDA correctly follows the sum rule $\int n(r_i, r_j) = -1$. That is, one electron's charge is excluded from the vicinity of electron located at r . Moreover, $\epsilon_x[n(r)]$

is underestimated whilst $\epsilon_c[n(r)]$ is overestimated, on average, these inaccuracies somewhat cancel out each other.

In spin polarized materials, densities in separate spin channels differ, so LDA is incompatible for magnetic materials. To combat this, spin was introduced to LDA, resulting in local spin density approximation (LSDA). Thus, the total density is thereby split into two densities, $n_\uparrow(r)$ and $n_\downarrow(r)$, which indicate density in the spin-up (SU) and spin-down (SD) channels, respectively. The ϵ_{xc} from LSDA scheme is given by;

$$\epsilon_{xc}^{LSDA} = \int \{n_\uparrow(r) + n_\downarrow(r)\} \epsilon_{xc}[n_\uparrow(r) + n_\downarrow(r)] dr \quad (2.21)$$

In 1996 Kohn et al showed that the physical properties of a system at r are dependent on the particles in the neighbourhood of r and don't demonstrate significant variation corresponding to changes in potential outside of this region [52]. Any approximations, thus, should be local or quasi-local in nature, and not global. This gives a delayed justification for the success of LDA/LSDA approximation. The problem with LDA/LSDA is it underestimates the band gap by even by 40% in certain cases whilst overestimates chemical binding [53]. In order to overcome the problems, some extensions of the original approximation were introduced.

2.9 Generalized Gradient Approximations (GGA)

The first extension of LDA is GGA which takes local fluctuations of the density $n(r)$ into consideration. The ϵ_{xc} by GGA scheme is given by

$$\epsilon_{xc}^{GGA}[n(r)] = \int \epsilon_{xc}^{GGA} f[n(r), |\nabla n(r)|] n(r) dr \quad (2.22)$$

Although GGA incorporates a gradient of density functional into its formulism, it is still a local function, as it takes density in close neighborhood of r into account. Depending on how the $f[n(r), |\nabla n(r)|]$ functional is parameterized, different versions of the GGA have been constructed. Much popular versions of

GGA is one parameterized by Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof PBE-GGA [54]. The GGA methods extends DFT to inhomogeneous systems, making it more practical. GGA, like LDA, follows the sum rule and outperforms LDA . However, GGA formulism doesn't effectively estimate the magneto-electronic structure of correlated systems. As a result, LDA's serious shortcoming of underestimating the band gap still exists. The inconsistency in experimental and computational band profile by GGA method results because of self-interaction effect and insufficient potential to deal with localized states.

2.10 Modified Becke-Johnson Potentials

To overcome the GGA limitations and estimate the band gap near to the experimental results, there are a variety of approaches available. Hubbard potentials (U) [55] or modified Becke-Johnson potentials (mBJ) [56] can be integrated with LDA/GGA, self-interaction correction methods have also been suggested [57], or even alternative hybrid functional [58] can be utilized. Hybrid approaches, however, are more expensive and provide satisfactory results for limited cases. Furthermore, rather than being ab-initio, U-parameter and hybrid functions are semi-empirical. However, within ab-initio framework, Becke and Johnson potential is a suitable because it is a computationally cheap method that yields band gaps near to the experimental band gaps. Becke and Johnson designed a potential [59] to replicate the exact shape of optimized effective potential later on modified by Becke and Johnson (mBJ). Although mBJ potential outperforms LDA and GGA, the improvements were moderate [60,61]. To boost the mBJ exchange potential it was further modified and a parameter that allows to adjust relative weights of kinetic energy and potential energy in the BJ potential. The modified-BJ potential reads [62]

$$V^{mBj}(r) = CV^{BR}(r) + (3C - 2) \sqrt{\frac{5}{6}} \sqrt{\frac{t(r)}{n(r)}} \quad (2.23)$$

Where $t(r)$ is the kinetic energy density and $V^{BR}(r)$ is the Becke-Roussel potential and C is screening parameter given by;

$$C = \alpha + \beta \left(\frac{1}{\Omega} \int d^3r \frac{|\nabla \rho(r)|}{\rho(r)} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (2.24)$$

α and β are free parameters having values $\alpha = -0.012$ and $\beta = 1.023$ bohrs within the WIEN2k code. The TB-mBJ potential is able to yield energy band gaps in most semiconductors and insulators with high accuracy. It is suitable not only for sp -based semiconductors only, but also for correlated TM-based compounds. The great accuracy and predictive power might be obtained by extracting the parameter C uniquely from the electron density of the particular system. The method is computationally inexpensive, and its quantitative predictive value is typically comparable (or even better) than that of far more complicated and expensive methods.

2.11 From Theory to Computer Simulations

Quantum mechanical computations play a crucial role in order to understand the characteristics features of materials. We showed in the foregoing discussion that under certain approximations $n(r)$ is enough to analyse the physical properties. While doing the computation we have employed the periodic nature of the solids assuming that they are perfect, highly ordered, and infinite; but in reality, experimentally grown crystals deviate from this ideal stoichiometry. However, under periodic boundary conditions one can characterize the infinite crystal by analyzing the properties in a single unit cell. Calculations can be simplified by employing translational space group symmetry operations (such a, translation, inversion, rotation, or using mirror planes) that leave the ideal crystal invariant.

2.12 Periodic potential and Bloch Theorem

In the beginning of electronic theory, electrons in a solid were thought to be free particles with plane wave ($\sim e^{ikx}$) properties. However, in the crystalline solid,

positive ion cores are periodically arranged over lattice positions. As a result, instead of constant, the electrons pass through a periodic potential; $V_{\text{ext}}(r) = V_{\text{ext}}(r + a)$. Bloch proposed that an electronic wave function must be more than just a free wave and should include a modulating element. As a result, he expressed it as the product of cell-periodic part and plane wave given by [63];

$$\psi_e(r) = u_k(r)e^{ikx} \quad (2.25)$$

The modulating factor follows the periodic condition of lattice i.e., $u_k(r) = u_k(r + a)$. The physical interpretation of the Bloch theorem is that $\psi_e(r)$ and $\psi_e(r + a)$ are almost identical, except for a phase factor e^{ika} , but the probability density is identical $|\psi_e(r)|^2 = |\psi_e(r + a)|^2$. Thus, the Bloch theorem suggests that it is not essential to identify the electron wave function everywhere; it is sufficient to determine it in a single unit cell because the wave function has a periodic nature and is identical in neighboring cells except for the phase factor. Due to periodicity of potential and cell-periodic part, the wave function can be represented as a Fourier Series summed over all the allowed wave vectors

$$\psi_e(r) = \sum_k C(k)e^{ikx} \quad (2.26)$$

2.13 Simulation Code

To approximate the physical properties of materials, we used the WIEN2k Code [63] and programmers integrated to it like BoltzTraP code [64], Cubic elastic package [65] and Gibbs2 code [66]. The WIEN2k is based on DFT formalism to compute the electrical structure of materials. The original code, WIEN, was created in 1990 by Peter Blaha and arlheinzh Schwarz at Vienna University of Technology in Austria. [67]. The code relies on the full-potential linearized augmented plane-wave (FPLAPW) basis approach. The subsequent releases were WIEN93, WIEN97, and finally upgraded to WIEN2k. WIEN2k can estimate a wide variety of properties such as electronic structure, photoelectron spectroscopy, magnetism, spin orbital coupling, charge density distribution,

chemical binding characteristics, and so on with high precision. The detailed discussion of obtaining the above-mentioned properties using WIEN2k is reported elsewhere [68].

2.14 Cubic Elastic Package

Elastic constants signify the mechanical response to deforming force by expressing the relationship between the stress (χ_{ij}) and strain (e_{ij}) components for solids. When an external force (stress) is applied to a system, it produces a strain (the relative deformation); similarly, when a system is strained in some way, it produces stress. Within the elastic regime, χ_{ij} is linearly proportional to e_{ij} - Hooke's law, elastic constants (C_{ij}) are proportionality constants. χ_{ij} and e_{ij} are second order tensors with nine components each; consequently, the C_{ij} 's are fourth order tensors with eighty-one components. In general, the symmetric nature of χ_{ij} and e_{ij} components, decreases the number of required elastic constants to twenty-one. Besides this, the crystal symmetry further reduces minimum required elastic constants to fully describe the mechanical behaviour. In this study we have worked with cubic DPs, cubic system requires only three C_{11}, C_{12} and C_{44} elastic constants. Longitudinal compression C_{11} is the proportional constant between χ_{11} and e_{11} . Transverse expansion C_{12} is the proportional constant between χ_{11} and e_{22} . C_{11} and C_{12} can thereby be simulated from a single stress component χ_{11} while monitoring two components of strain e_{11} and e_{22} . Shear elastic constant C_{44} is the proportional constant between χ_{12} and e_{12} . C_{ij} 's can be computed either by analysing stress or total energy as a function of the strain. The two approaches are conceptually comparable, except that stress is a linear function of strain while energy is a quadratic function of strain. The improvement of the DFT technique has enabled *ab* – initio analysis of the elastic characteristics of crystalline solids; elastic parameters, in turn, provide considerable knowledge about materials. Elastic constants can be used to

easily identify properties such as binding characteristics and reaction to load. As a result, it is beneficial from the device fabrication point of view.

The WIEN2k code contains a Programme for calculating the elastic parameters of various structures such as cubic, hexagonal, and orthorhombic. We employed the Cubic elastic package for the cubic DPs, which is an energy approach interfaced to the WIEN2k code. An elastic solid's total energy can be altered by applying volumetric or distortional strain. Within elastic regime, expansion of energy about the unstrained situation for small deformations is;

$$E(V, \delta) = E_0 + V_0 \left(\sum_i^6 \chi_i e_i + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j}^6 C_{ij} e_i e_j \right) \quad (2.27)$$

The C_{ij} 's can be calculated by taking the second-order partial derivatives of equation 3.31 with respect to strains, at zero strain.

$$C_{ij} = \left. \frac{\partial^2 E(V, \delta)}{\partial \delta_i \partial \delta_j} \right|_{\delta=0} \quad (2.28)$$

Three different kinds of appropriate strains are applied to optimized structure: Volume conserving - Orthorhombic and Monoclinic strains; Shape conserving - Cubic strains. These deformations correspondingly reveal C_{11} , C_{12} and C_{44} respectively. The deformation matrices and energy changes associated with each type of strain effect are described in the original paper by Jamal et al [66]. If deformation increases the energy of the system, it leads towards instability; however, if the deformation energy is negative, then deformed state is more stable. As a result, deformation energy must be positive in order to ensure mechanical stability. This constrains the values of elastic constants to follow certain criteria, which are formally defined as necessary stability conditions [69]. The dynamical stability of the cubic structure demands:

$$C_{11} - C_{12} > 0; C_{11} + 2C_{12} > 0; C_{44} > 0; C_{11} > 0; C_{11}^2 - C_{12}^2 > 0 \quad (2.29)$$

Once C_{ij} 's are computed one can look for other elastic parameters. In general, elastic modulus represents the stress-to-strain ratio. The ratio of normal stress to

volumetric strain is Bulk modulus ($B_0 = (C_{11} + C_{12})/3$), it signifies the ability of material to resist volumetric deformation.

Shear modulus (G) is the ratio of shear stress to shear strain. The magnitude of G can be estimated by using Voigt's and Reuss' formulism $G_V = (C_{11} - C_{12} + 3G_{44})/5$ and $G_R = \{5C_{44}(C_{11} - C_{12})\}/\{4C_{44} + 3(C_{11} - C_{12})\}$, respectively. G_V defines the iso-strain upper bound, whilst G_R signifies the iso-stress lower bound [70]. Combining the G_V and G_R equations with the Hill's averaging approach yields an intermediate value $G = (G_V + G_R)/2$ [70]. It is easier to alter a material's structure if the share stress is lower. For an isotropic crystal $G = C_{44}$. Using the values of B_0 and G , one can obtain Young's modulus ($Y = 9BG/(3B_0 + G)$) and Poisson's ratio ($\nu = (3B_0 - Y)/6B_0$) [71]. Y represents the ratio of normal stress to longitudinal strain and quantifies an elastic solid's resistance to a change in length. When a material is squeezed (stretched) in one direction, it expands (contracts) in other two perpendicular orientations (stretching). This is referred to as the Poisson effect, thereby ν describes the ratio of a material's relative lateral expansion (compression) to its relative longitudinal compression (expansion) [72]. Straight from the C_{ij} 's values one can deduce anisotropic factor $A' = 2C_{44}/(C_{11} - C_{12})$ which is helpful in charactering anisotropic nature of materials. Moreover, sound velocities and Debye temperature along principal axes (100), (110) and (111) directions can be computed following the mathematical relations reported elsewhere [73].

2.15 Transport properties

To evaluate the thermoelectric efficiency of the examined materials, the figure of merit zT is necessary, which is dependent on S , κ and σ . These coefficients are simulated using the BoltzTrap algorithm in collaborated with WIEN2k. The Boltzmann transport equation is solved under the assumption of constant relaxation time approximation (CRTA). Over the years, CRTA is found to

provide effective results [74,75]. According to the Boltzmann transport equation, in the steady state, the distribution function $f(r, k, t)$, which specifies the probability of finding an electron at position r with crystal momentum k at time t , does not change. At the steady state, the changes in $f(r, k, t)$ due the effect of fields, diffusion, and collisions are zero. Mathematically it states;

$$\left. \frac{\partial f(r, k, t)}{\partial t} \right|_{\text{field}} + \left. \frac{\partial f(r, k, t)}{\partial t} \right|_{\text{Diffusion}} + \left. \frac{\partial f(r, k, t)}{\partial t} \right|_{\text{Collision}} = 0 \quad (2.30)$$

The BoltzTrap calculations are based on evaluating the transport distribution function $\Xi(\varepsilon, T) = \int \sum_n v_{nk} \otimes v_{nk} \tau_{nk} \delta(\varepsilon - \varepsilon_{nk}) \frac{d^3k}{8\pi^3}$ using a fine k -mesh. To derive the group velocities $v_{nk} = \frac{1}{\hbar} \frac{\partial \varepsilon_{nk}}{\partial k} = \frac{1}{m} \langle k | p | k \rangle$ or quasi particle energies over a fine k -mesh, BoltzTrap hinges on Fourier sums to interpolate the eigen values. Once $\Xi(\varepsilon, T)$ function is defined the temperature and potential dependent transport coefficients can be determined by simple numerical integration

$$\sigma = e^2 \int E(\varepsilon) \left(-\frac{\partial f_0}{\partial \varepsilon} \right) d\varepsilon \quad (2.31)$$

$$\kappa = \frac{1}{T} \int E(\varepsilon) \left(-\frac{\partial f_0}{\partial \varepsilon} \right) (\varepsilon - \mu)^2 d\varepsilon \quad (2.32)$$

$$S = \frac{e}{T\sigma} \int \Xi(\varepsilon) \left(-\frac{\partial f_0}{\partial \varepsilon} \right) (\varepsilon - \mu) d\varepsilon \quad (2.33)$$

here, μ is the chemical potential and τ_k is the relaxation time.

2.16 Phonon calculations

In crystalline solids, the lattice vibrations are described using the language of normal modes or phonons. The lattice dynamics problem involves the calculation of phonon frequencies (eigenvalues) and phonon eigenvectors. The calculation of phonon frequencies of solids is important to understand and predict the properties or phenomena where lattice degrees of freedom are playing essential role. Such properties or phenomena include thermodynamical properties, phase stability,

thermal expansion, transport properties and superconductivity etc.,. Using the first-principles calculations the phonon properties can be calculated [76-78]. There are two methods of phonon calculations which are mainly used viz. density functional perturbation theory (DFPT) method and direct method. In DFPT, force constants are computed in reciprocal space by applying the linear response theory to the KS equations to see the effect of slight perturbations. In the direct method, the supercell approach is mostly used to get the force constants in real space. Typically, DFT is used to get the forces on nuclei as derivative of energy with respect to positions. Here, the supercell approach of phonon calculation is discussed which is mainly used in the thesis.

In a perfect crystal at rest, the equilibrium position of the κ^{th} ion in the l^{th} unit cell be $\mathbf{r}(l\kappa)$. The displacement of $\mathbf{u}(l\kappa)$ from equilibrium position generates ionic vibration and then the potential energy Φ will depends on displacement as follows [76-78]

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi = & \Phi_0 + \sum_{l\kappa} \sum_{\alpha} \Phi_{\alpha}(l\kappa) u_{\alpha}(l\kappa) + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{ll'\kappa\kappa'} \sum_{\alpha\beta} \Phi_{\alpha\beta}(l\kappa, l'\kappa') u_{\alpha}(l\kappa) u_{\beta}(l'\kappa') \\ & + \frac{1}{3!} \sum_{ll'l''\kappa\kappa'\kappa''} \sum_{\alpha\beta\gamma} \Phi_{\alpha\beta\gamma}(l\kappa, l'\kappa', l''\kappa'') \times u_{\alpha}(l\kappa) u_{\beta}(l'\kappa') u_{\gamma}(l''\kappa'') + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (2.34)$$

where α, β, γ are the Cartesian indices. Here the zeroth, first, second order force constants are $\Phi_0, \Phi_{\alpha}(l\kappa)$ and $\Phi_{\alpha\beta}(l\kappa, l'\kappa')$ respectively. The third order (or anharmonic) force constant is given by $\Phi_{\alpha\beta\gamma}(l\kappa, l'\kappa', l''\kappa'')$. In harmonic phonon calculations only terms upto second order are considered in understanding the vibrations of the crystals due to small displacements. This approximation is called harmonic approximation. The higher order terms are called anharmonic terms and they are taken care through the perturbation theory.

The force (first order force constant) can be obtained from the potential energy as,

$$F_{\alpha}(l\kappa) = -\frac{\partial\Phi}{\partial u_{\alpha}(l\kappa)} \quad (2.35)$$

Then a second order force constant $\Phi_{\alpha\beta}(l\kappa, l'\kappa')$ using the above equation is written as,

$$\frac{\partial^2\Phi}{\partial u_{\alpha}(l\kappa)\partial u_{\beta}(l'\kappa')} = -\frac{\partial F_{\beta}(l'\kappa')}{\partial u_{\alpha}(l\kappa)} \quad (2.36)$$

The eigen value solution of dynamical matrix $D(\mathbf{q})$ provides us phonon eigenvalues (frequencies) and eigenvectors under harmonic approximation as

$$D(\mathbf{q})\mathbf{W}_{\mathbf{q}j} = \omega_{\mathbf{q}j}^2\mathbf{W}_{\mathbf{q}j} \quad \text{or} \quad \sum_{\beta\kappa'} D_{\kappa\kappa'}^{\alpha\beta}(\mathbf{q})W_{\mathbf{q}j}^{\beta\kappa'} = \omega_{\mathbf{q}j}^2W_{\mathbf{q}j}^{\alpha\kappa} \quad (2.37)$$

with $D_{\kappa\kappa'}^{\alpha\beta}(\mathbf{q})$ given by,

$$D_{\kappa\kappa'}^{\alpha\beta}(\mathbf{q}) = \sum_{l'} \frac{\Phi_{\alpha\beta}(0\kappa, l'\kappa')}{\sqrt{m_{\kappa}m_{\kappa'}}} W^{i\mathbf{q}} \cdot [\mathbf{r}(l'\kappa') - \mathbf{r}(0\kappa)] \quad (2.38)$$

In the above expressions, m_{κ} represents ionic mass for ion κ , $\omega_{\mathbf{q}j}$ and $\mathbf{W}_{\mathbf{q}j}$ represent phonon frequency and polarization vector of a phonon mode with the wave vector \mathbf{q} and branch index j .

The phonon density of states is obtained as [76],

$$g(\omega) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{\mathbf{q}j} \delta(\omega - \omega_{\mathbf{q}j}) \quad (2.39)$$

where, N represents the number of unit cells. The energy of the phonon system at a temperature T using the calculated phonon frequencies is obtained as,

$$E = \sum_{\mathbf{q}j} \hbar\omega_{\mathbf{q}j} \left[\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\exp(\hbar\omega_{\mathbf{q}j}/k_B T) - 1} \right] \quad (2.40)$$

\hbar is the reduced Planck constant and k_B is the Boltzmann constant.

The group velocity of a phonon mode $\lambda = (\mathbf{q}, j)$ with branch index j and wave vector \mathbf{q} is related to phonon frequency as

$$v_{\alpha} = \frac{\partial\omega_{\lambda}}{\partial q_{\alpha}} \quad (2.41)$$

The phonon thermodynamical quantities at finite temperature T viz. constant volume specific heat c_v , Helmholtz free energy F and entropy S can be obtained once the phonon frequencies are known. The dependence of temperature is introduced through the Bose-Einstein distribution function. The relation of the above quantities to the phonon mode frequencies are given below [76]

- 1 Constant volume specific heat

$$c_v = \sum_{\lambda} c_{\lambda} = k_B \left(\frac{\hbar\omega_{\lambda}}{k_B T} \right)^2 \frac{\exp(\hbar\omega_{\lambda}/k_B T)}{[\exp(\hbar\omega_{\lambda}/k_B T) - 1]^2} \quad (2.42)$$

- 2 Helmholtz free-energy,

$$F_{ph} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\mathbf{q}j} \hbar\omega_{\mathbf{q}j} + k_B T \sum_{\mathbf{q}j} \ln \left[1 - \exp \left(- \frac{\hbar\omega_{\mathbf{q}j}}{k_B T} \right) \right] \quad (2.43)$$

- 3 Entropy,

$$S = \frac{1}{2T} \sum_{\mathbf{q}j} \hbar\omega_{\mathbf{q}j} \coth[\hbar\omega_{\mathbf{q}j}/2k_B T] - k_B \sum_{\mathbf{q}j} \ln[2 \sinh(\hbar\omega_{\mathbf{q}j}/2k_B T)] \quad (2.44)$$

The thermal expansion of a crystal is an anharmonic property. However, it can be approximately calculated under an approximation called quasi-harmonic approximation (QHA) accounting for the anharmonic effect [79]. Under harmonic approximation, there is no interaction among phonons due to which phonon frequencies do not depend on the volume and hence the volume does not change with temperature. So, in QHA the volume dependence of phonon frequency is introduced by calculating phonon properties at different volumes simply under harmonic approximation. The free energy in QHA is written as [79],

$$F^{QHA}(T; V) = U_{el}(V) + F_{ph}(T; V) \quad (2.45)$$

where, $U_{el}(V)$ is the minimum electronic total energy and $F_{ph}(T; V)$ is the phonon part of Helmholtz free energy at temperature T and volume V . The equilibrium lattice parameter at a given temperature can be obtained by minimizing the free energy curve (Eq. 2.60).

The coefficient of thermal expansion $\beta(T)$ can be estimated once the values of equilibrium volume at different temperatures are obtained.

$$\beta(T) = \frac{1}{V(T)} \left(\frac{\partial V(T)}{\partial T} \right)_P \quad (2.46)$$

In semiconductors or insulators phonons are the major carriers of heat which mainly contribute to the thermal conductivity. This lattice contribution of thermal conductivity κ_{ph} can be calculated using first-principles phonon calculations. The method used in this thesis work to compute κ_{ph} using phono3py [80] is discussed here. The closed form of κ_{ph} which can be obtained after solving linearized BTE under single mode relaxation time approximation (SMRT) is

$$\kappa_{ph} = \frac{1}{NV_0} \sum_{\lambda} c_{\lambda} \mathbf{v}_{\lambda} \otimes \mathbf{v}_{\lambda} \tau_{\lambda}^{SMRT} \quad (2.47)$$

where, N and V_0 are the respective number and volume of unit cell, c_{λ} is mode heat capacity, \mathbf{v}_{λ} is the mode group velocity and τ_{λ}^{SMRT} is the lifetime of phonon mode λ . The terms, c_{λ} (Eq. 2.57) and \mathbf{v}_{λ} (Eq. 2.56) are obtained under harmonic approximation using the supercell approach as discussed earlier. However, in harmonic approximation phonon-phonon interaction is not present and hence phonons have infinite lifetime (and κ_{ph}). Therefore, to calculate the phonon-phonon interactions and lifetime the third-order force constants (anharmonic terms) are considered using perturbation theory. This anharmonic phonon calculation is discussed in the next section.

2.17 Simulation in one dimension (SCAPS-1D)

For the efficient solar cell configuration, optimal design is an essential factor. SCAPS-1D simulator for a $p-n$ diode provides visualization of analytical solutions [81, 82]. SCAPS-1D solves the recombination and generation term which comprises of the couples Poisson and continuity equations in one dimension. Consequently, we can obtain a graphical result as well as the associated data. A 3D model requires a huge memory, energy, and time for

simulation. A periodic version with proper boundary contains 1D model computationally efficient and similarly accurate. One dimension Poisson and continuity equation solver like SCAPS, AFORS-HET, AMPS, and PC1D simulator could simulate the p - n junction reliability. The photo-generated carrier changes the electric field, band bending in the overall device under the effect of illumination. The equilibrium electrostatic behaviour of the device in dark changes to transient, and complex phenomena like tunnelling mechanism under illumination. If a design is not addressing these photo-generated issues, it may obstruct the photovoltaic performance in unforeseen ways. The advantage of simulation lies in the gaining of insight, which clarifies some nonintuitive experimental observations.

SCAPS (Solar Cell Capacitance Simulator) is a one-dimensional (1D) Poisson equation solver package for simulating solar cells, developed at the University of Gent, Belgium, Department of Electronics and Information System (ELIS) by a team of Alex Niemegeers, Stefaan Degraeve, Koen Decock, Johan Verschraegen and Marc Burgelman. I highly acknowledge them for making it freely assessable to the research community. It solves the basic one-dimensional Poisson equation and the continuity equations, and other related semiconductor equation for electrons and holes through junction and interfaces. The system of equation (1-3) is numerically solved, using the Gummel iteration scheme with Newton-Raphson sub steps.

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\epsilon_0 \epsilon \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x} \right) = -q \left(p - n + N_D^+ - N_D^- + \frac{\rho_{def}}{q} \right) \quad (2.48)$$

$$-\frac{\partial J_n}{\partial x} - U_n + G = \frac{\partial n}{\partial t}; \quad J_n = -\frac{u_n n}{q} \frac{\partial E_{Fn}}{\partial x} \quad (2.49)$$

$$-\frac{\partial J_p}{\partial x} - U_p + G = \frac{\partial p}{\partial t}; \quad J_p = -\frac{u_p p}{q} \frac{\partial E_{Fp}}{\partial x} \quad (2.50)$$

Coupled differential equations in (ϕ, n, p) or (ϕ, E_{Fn}, E_{Fp}) . Where ϕ electrostatic potential, q is an electrical charge, ϵ_r is relative permittivity, ϵ_0 is the permittivity in vacuum, p is hole density, n is electron density, N_D is density of charged impurities of donor and N_A is acceptor density, ρ_p and ρ_n are holes and electrons distribution, G is the generation rate, J_n and J_p are the electron and hole current density respectively. It makes use of the Shah-Shockley theory for bulk recombination and Pauwels-Vanhoutte theory for interface recombination. In SCAPS-1D, the user specifies device configuration comprising semiconductor layers (up to seven layers), related material properties of layers are submitted through intuitive GUI. Initially, a one-dimensional mesh is implemented on all the layers of structure to be simulated, and all the layers are partitioned into a number of nodes and grid points, and then the basic solving of the equations at the junctions and interfaces are implemented. It solves these equations for calculating the ac and dc measurements for $I(V)$, $C(V)$, $C(f)$, Quantum efficiency curve, admittance measurement, band diagram, recombination in illumination in p-n heterojunctions structures. It can model the various tunnelling and multivalent defect generally relevant in the thin-film solar cell. Thus the effect of absorption, band offset and band alignments (conduction band and valence bands), inter-band tunnelling (band to band, intra-band, to interface defects and contacts) in dc problems only using WKB-approximation, defects energy levels and recombination can suitably be illustrated by this software package in thin-film solar cells. This numerical simulator provides visualization of analytical solutions running in the background. Also, the phenomena of impurity photovoltaics IPV, multijunction, split spectrum with variation in illumination intensity, grading for all parameters, tunnelling, and various defects level in bulk interfaces can be simulated by SCAPS-1 D. It also provides an advanced features of script language and script files to run user defined simulation and could be built by the user further. The layer thickness, graded bandgap, temperature dependence of

parameters, composition grading, defects (multivalent defects, neutral defects, energetic distribution of defect level, interface, tunnelling). Capacitance simulation of the structure/junction and conduction simulations are calculated using a small-signal analysis at the working point conditions. The electrostatic behavior of device changes under illumination due to the photo generated carriers, local electric field, and generation of band bending in the overall device. The SCAPS 1D is sufficiently capable of simulating these local effects and gives pragmatically accurate results. This gives an advantage of, gaining insight, which clarifies some non-intuitive experimental observations. A straight forward application of this software is in the optimization of the solar cell in terms of configuration, like thickness and bandgap optimization of various layers, optimization of band gap grading, etc. Additional physics simulations include: (a) baselining of device performance by a proper defect modelling to replicate the experimental observation of voltage pinning in temperature dependence experiment, (b) various abnormalities in I-V characteristics (crossover, rollover, etc.), and (c) QE performance of a specific configuration with varying illumination and voltage biasing conditions, to bring out the physical understanding related to the electronic behaviour of solar cell structure. Work in this direction of theoretical modelling using SCAPS could be helpful for the thin-film solar cell community working on various types of solar cells including CIGS, CdTe, Perovskite, Si, and CZTS.

2.18 Steps to simulate the SCAPS

After launching, the SCAPS the window appears shown in figure 2.1 . The sequential steps to run a simulation are enumerated (1-6). In step 1, the device configuration is defined. Each layer, material parameters along with the recombination parameters and defects types are entered in this step. Step 2 defines the working point condition like temperature, voltage, resistances, illumination intensity, spectrum etc. The neutral density (ND) filter could be used to vary the

illumination intensity (T) as given by $T = 100 \times 10^{-ND}$. The reflection at the back contact can be implemented if needed. Using spectrum space, the electron-hole profile is generated. In step 3, the user defined profile is entered. In step 4, various simulations like electrical I-V, QE, C-V, admittance (C-f) can be performed. The range of measurement and resolution can be specified. Step 5 provides for the single-shot batch setup (as per the scripts file/user defined requirements). It provides a batch setup where the dependency of a performance parameters on multiple parameters can be studied. Using recorder, the relation of material parameters on various other design parameters is simulated. These are shown in figure 2.2. The curve fitting of various measurements like the Nyquist plot, Mott-Schottky plot, etc. can also be implemented here. In step 6, various output files including I-V, band diagram, generation recombination profile, curve fitting, etc. can be obtained.

2.19 Limitation of 1D Simulation

Here, it is worthwhile to mention the limitations of SCAPS 1D. These are enumerated below:

- (i) For the purpose of fast calculation and low memory usage, the SCAPS solves the equation in 1D. SCAPS have calculation/converges issues when multiple junctions are simulated (like pnp, npn, etc.). Up to seven layers of the structure only could be configured at the moment.
- (ii) The simulation diverges at high forward voltages, a similar issue as with most of the other simulation programs.
- (iii) SCAPS does not simulate time-domain variation or transient phenomena. (For e.g. it cannot simulate the forward and reverse scan hysteresis in case of perovskite SC).
- (iv) Visible light interference phenomena or simulation of optical confinement (ray tracing) are not simulated.

- (v) It does not accommodate the optical losses (reflection, non-absorption, thermalization losses, metal bus-bars area loss, etc.)

Figure 2.1 Working steps of SCAPS-1D

Figure 2.2: Batch set up of SCAPS 1D